

DEVELOPMENT OF A METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE ADHESION FORCE OF COTTON FIBER TO SEEDS

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Abstract: in this article, a method for determining the adhesion force of fiber to seed was developed for the Andijan-36 variety grown in Andijan and the 52-4, China-31, China-29, and 52 selection varieties imported from China, and the optimal sample mass variant was determined.

Keywords: quantity of tangled and complex tangled fiber, number of damaged or injured seeds, quantity of cortex fiber, nodules, fine and coarse impurities

1. Introduction

When processing various selection varieties at cotton ginning enterprises, different types of defects and waste are produced: under the influence of technological processes, these include tangled and complex tangled fiber, damaged or injured seeds, cortex fiber, nodules, and fine and coarse impurities.

Two defects in cotton fiber are considered harmful: cortex fiber and nodules. Eliminating these during the spinning process is complex. The primary cause of cortex fiber formation is that drying cotton at high temperatures creates openings in the outer layer of the seed, preventing internal moisture from escaping during drying, which leads to defect formation. The second main reason is that when separating fiber from seeds across different selection varieties at ginning enterprises, the adhesion force of the fiber to the seed varies, and the structure, geometric properties, and firmness of the seed also differ by selection variety.

When processing various selection varieties at cotton ginning enterprises, particularly during ginning, the fiber is separated from the seed under uniform force. This leads to an increase in cortex fiber and deterioration of finished product quality.

2. Methods

A separate optimal procedure needed to be developed for each selection variety during the ginning process at cotton ginning enterprises. Experimental work was carried out to develop a method for determining the adhesion force of fiber to seed for different selection varieties, in order to study the causes of cortex fiber formation. For this purpose, samples of 100 gr, 150 gr, 200 gr, 250 gr, and 300 gr were taken; seeds from each sample were removed and combed first with a coarse-toothed comb then a fine-toothed comb. Tufts were formed along the chalaza, lateral, and micropyle sections of the seed, and in the DSh-3M tearing device the adhesion force of fiber to the sample seed was determined. The distance between clamps was 3 mm. The number of fibers was counted using an MBI-6 biological microscope.

The adhesion force of fiber tufts attached to the chalaza, lateral, and micropyle sections of the seed was determined using the following formula.

$$P_{yr} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n n_i} \quad \text{sN} \quad (1)$$

The adhesion force of a single fiber was determined using the following formula.

$$P_1 = \frac{P_1}{n_1}; P_2 = \frac{P_2}{n_2}; \dots; P_{10} = \frac{P_{10}}{n_{10}} \quad \text{sN} \quad (2)$$

Here $\sum_{i=1}^n P_i$ — bundle adhesion force, sN; $\sum_{i=1}^n n_i$ — number of fibers; P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{10} — adhesion force of each tuft, sN; n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{10} — number of fibers in each tuft.

The average adhesion force of a single fiber is determined using the following formula:

$$P_{o'it} = \frac{\sum P_i}{10} = \frac{(P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 + P_5 + P_6 + P_7 + P_8 + P_9 + P_{10})}{10} \quad \text{sN} \quad (3)$$

Based on the obtained results, experiments were conducted to develop the method for determining fiber adhesion force to seed, and the results were subjected to mathematical-statistical processing.

As is known from mathematical statistics, absolute and relative errors arise when determining random indicators in experiments.

The average mass of fuzzy seeds was determined using the following formula.

$$m_{yr} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n n_i} \quad \text{gr} \quad (4)$$

Here $\sum_{i=1}^n m_i$ — mass of fuzzy seeds, gr; $\sum_{i=1}^n n_i$ — number of fuzzy seeds.

The absolute error ε is the difference between the random value determined from measurement m_2 and the true value m_1 .

$$\varepsilon = m_1 - m_2 \quad (5)$$

Here: m_1 — mass of the taken sample, mg; m_2 — mass of the sample participating in tearing relative to the fiber mass released by combing during stapling, mg.

The relative error δ is the ratio of the absolute error to the measurement result value.

$$\delta = \frac{\varepsilon}{m_{yr}} \cdot 100\% \quad (6)$$

Accuracy and reliability are of great importance when evaluating indicators in scientific research. The confidence interval characterizes the accuracy and reliability of the measured indicator values.

After determining the adhesion force of fiber to seed, its dispersion and coefficient of variation were determined using the formulas given below.

3. Results

The confidence interval of the true mean value

$$\eta_H = \bar{P} - \varepsilon \{ \tilde{P} \}_0 \leq \eta_H = \bar{P} + \varepsilon \{ \tilde{P} \}_0 \quad (7)$$

In the statistical processing of experimental results, the fiber adhesion force indicator to seed was determined in the following order.

The average sample value \tilde{P} is determined as the arithmetic mean using the following formula:

$$\tilde{P} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^n P_i \quad (8)$$

Here m — sample mass, gr; P_i — measured values of the random indicator.

Variance

$$S^2 \{ \tilde{P} \} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \tilde{P})^2 \quad (9)$$

The coefficient of variation $CV\{P\}$ and quadratic non-uniformity were determined using the following formulas.

$$S\{P\} = \frac{S(P)}{\tilde{P}} \quad (10)$$

$$CV\{V\} = \frac{S(P)}{\tilde{P}} \cdot 100\% \quad (11)$$

The test results obtained from determining the adhesion force of fiber to seed for various selection varieties are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Indicators for determining the adhesion force of fiber to seed for various selection varieties

No/No.	No. of seeds, n	No. of fuzzy seeds, fuzzy seeds, avg. mass, m, mg	Bundle adhesion force, sN	Fibers per bundle, n	Single fiber fiber adhesion	Cortex fiber count, n	Absolute error, mg	Relative error, %
Andijan-36 selection variety								
Chalaza section of seed								
1.	10	125,4	630	786	0,80	5,0	7,6	5,80
2.	20	120,6	660	799	0,83	6,0	6,8	5,64
3.	30	120,8	640	765	0,84	8,0	7,0	5,79
4.	40	127,2	638	788	0,81	7,0	6,5	5,11
5.	50	139,8	648	802	0,81	6,0	6,3	4,51
	Average	122,2	643	788	0,82	7,0	6,8	5,37
Lateral section of seed								
1.	10	128,9	721	826	0,87	2,0	7,2	5,59

2.	20	125,4	739	808	0,91	3,0	7,0	5,58
3.	30	130,3	746	836	0,89	3,0	7,3	5,60
4.	40	125,6	757	812	0,93	1,0	6,7	5,33
5.	50	127,6	761	800	0,95	1,0	6,1	4,78
	Average	119,8	745	816	0,91	2,0	6,9	5,38
Micropyle section of seed								
1.	10	118,7	891	900	0,99	1,0	7,7	6,49
2.	20	123,6	921	904	1,02	-	7,6	6,15
3.	30	126,3	919	916	1,00	-	7,2	5,70
4.	40	127,3	913	908	1,00	-	7,0	5,50
5.	50	125,3	930	910	1,02	-	6,1	4,87
	Average	123,2	915	908	1,01	-	7,1	5,74
52-4 selection variety								
Chalaza section of seed								
1.	10	122,4	621	798	0,78	7,0	7,8	6,37
2.	20	125,6	616	786	0,78	8,0	7,3	5,81
3.	30	127,8	610	789	0,77	9,0	7,0	5,48
4.	40	122,8	609	743	0,82	8,0	6,6	5,37
5.	50	126,5	612	745	0,82	9,0	6,3	4,98
	Average	122,3	614	772	0,79	8,0	7,0	5,60
Lateral section of seed								
1.	10	115,6	746	820	0,91	2,0	7,2	6,23
2.	20	118,7	769	810	0,95	2,0	7,0	5,90
3.	30	127,8	780	808	0,97	2,0	6,9	5,40
4.	40	125,6	760	836	0,91	3,0	6,5	5,18
5.	50	126,8	744	822	0,90	4,0	6,3	4,97
	Average	123,9	760	820	0,93	3,0	6,8	5,54
Micropyle section of seed								
1.	10	112,8	941	910	1,03	-	7,6	6,74
2.	20	115,5	961	929	1,03	-	7,4	6,41
3.	30	114,9	951	910	1,04	-	7,2	6,27
4.	40	126,7	939	930	1,01	-	7,0	5,52
5.	50	125,8	946	920	1,03	-	6,2	4,93
	Average	122,1	948	919,8	1,03	-	7,1	5,97
China-31 selection variety								
Chalaza section of seed								
1.	10	120,7	628	756	0,83	8,0	8,5	7,04
2.	20	120,4	631	780	0,81	9,0	8,0	6,64
3.	30	123,5	609	782	0,79	9,0	7,8	6,32
4.	40	125,2	613	763	0,80	8,0	7,5	5,99
5.	50	130,4	606	767	0,79	7,0	6,5	4,98
	Average	123,2	617	770	0,80	8,0	7,7	6,19
Lateral section of seed								

1.	10	120,6	706	806	0,88	2,0	7,8	6,47
2.	20	116,9	713	816	0,87	2,0	7,5	6,41
3.	30	128,8	720	822	0,88	3,0	6,9	5,36
4.	40	120,5	719	816	0,88	1,0	6,2	5,15
5.	50	123,4	721	810	0,89	2,0	6,0	4,86
	Average	120,0	716	814	0,88	2,0	6,9	5,65
Micropyle section of seed								
1.	10	123,5	930	905	1,03	-	7,2	5,83
2.	20	126,6	928	912	1,02	-	7,4	5,84
3.	30	127,8	939	920	1,02	-	7,1	5,56
4.	40	126,4	920	890	1,03	-	7,0	5,53
5.	50	128,9	916	900	1,02	-	6,5	4,96
	Average	123,4	927	905	1,02	-	7,0	5,54
China-29 selection variety								
Chalaza section of seed								
1.	10	120,3	624	768	0,81	8,0	7,1	5,90
2.	20	125,6	606	788	0,77	8,0	6,4	5,09
3.	30	127,8	612	798	0,77	7,0	6,6	5,16
4.	40	120,5	638	767	0,83	9,0	6,1	5,06
5.	50	119,6	620	756	0,82	8,0	5,9	4,93
	Average	123,8	620	775	0,80	8,0	6,3	5,23
Lateral section of seed								
1.	10	120,6	745	822	0,91	3,0	6,8	5,64
2.	20	126,2	723	818	0,88	4,0	6,6	5,23
3.	30	125,1	721	829	0,87	3,0	6,3	5,04
4.	40	120,1	712	826	0,86	2,0	6,2	5,16
5.	50	122,0	759	838	0,91	3,0	6,1	5,00
	Average	122,8	732	827	0,89	3,0	6,4	5,21
Micropyle section of seed								
1.	10	125,6	930	904	1,03	-	7,3	5,81
2.	20	123,4	918	912	1,01	-	7,2	5,83
3.	30	120,9	922	905	1,02	-	6,8	5,62
4.	40	124,5	934	922	1,01	-	6,6	5,30
5.	50	126,7	905	916	0,99	-	6,3	4,97
	Average	124,2	922	912	1,01	-	6,8	5,51
52-4 selection variety								
Chalaza section of seed								
1.	10	119,6	616	705	0,87	7,0	7,6	6,35
2.	20	122,0	608	722	0,84	8,0	7,1	5,82
3.	30	125,6	612	734	0,83	8,0	6,8	5,41
4.	40	126,8	614	721	0,85	9,0	6,4	5,04
5.	50	128,9	620	720	0,86	7,0	6,1	4,73
	Average	124,6	614	720	0,85	8,0	6,8	5,47

Lateral section of seed								
1.	10	120,6	765	802	0,95	3,0	8,3	6,88
2.	20	122,2	734	831	0,88	2,0	7,8	6,38
3.	30	126,1	757	803	0,94	3,0	7,6	6,03
4.	40	127,2	740	808	0,91	4,0	7,3	5,74
5.	50	128,0	760	814	0,93	2,0	6,3	4,92
	Average	123,1	751	812	0,92	3,0	7,5	5,99
Micropyle section of seed								
1.	10	120,5	910	902	1,01	-	7,0	5,81
2.	20	124,6	918	906	1,01	-	7,2	5,78
3.	30	126,2	922	908	1,02	-	6,9	5,47
4.	40	119,8	930	899	1,03	-	6,8	5,68
5.	50	126,1	924	896	1,03	-	6,3	4,99
	Average	122,6	921	902	1,02	-	6,8	5,55

4. CONCLUSION

The research results on determining the adhesion force of fibers to seeds show that, firstly, looking at the seed sections, the adhesion force of fiber to seed is twice as high in the micropyle section compared to the chalaza section. This is because the void space in the chalaza section is larger relative to the seed kernel compared to the micropyle and lateral sections.

Secondly, our research shows that cortex fiber formation occurs more frequently precisely at the chalaza section of the seed.

Analyzing the adhesion force of cotton fiber to seed: for Andijan-36, the lateral section adhesion force increased by 13.7% and the micropyle section by 29.3% compared to the chalaza section; for 52-4, the lateral section increased by 19.2% and micropyle by 35.2%; for China-31, the lateral section increased by 13.8% and micropyle by 33.4%; for China-29, the lateral section increased by 15.3% and micropyle by 32.8%; for the 52 variety, the lateral section increased by 18.2% and micropyle by 33.3%.

Comparing by selection variety, relative to the cotton fiber indicators of the 100 gr sample from Andijan-36, the amount of cortex fiber, absolute error, and relative error in the 150 gr sample

The analysis results showed that for all selection varieties the sample mass was accepted as 300 gr, and the relative error was found to be between 4.3% and 4.9%.

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